

ENHANCING EXTENSION WORKER'S COMPETENCIES OF THE BACHELOR OF SCIENCE IN AGRICULTURE STUDENTS OF UNIVERSIDADE NACIONAL DE TIMOR LESTE

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Abstract

The study sought to examine the development of extension worker's competencies in the BSA program of Universidade Nacional de Timor Leste. It was conducted among 112 graduate students and selected faculty members. Data from the survey were processed and analyzed using descriptive statistic such as frequency counts and percentage computation. Interview excerpts that could be used to substantiate the research findings were highlighted and added to the discussions. Result showed that some research respondents and participants noted aspects for improvement in terms of the curriculum, the facilities, and the teaching strategies employed in the program. Moreover, the comparison results showed the gaps between the compared data. Accordingly, recommendations were forwarded to improve the extension workers' competencies of the university's graduates. Curriculum development is needed to fully optimize the learning environment for their current and incoming students, as well as the teaching practices of their faculties in the department.

Keywords: Extension Education, Extension Competencies, Employability.

INTRODUCTION

University graduates, regardless of the country they belong to, are competing in an environment shaped by local, national, as well as international expectations and standards. Among scopes of these "expectations", the impact of internationalization in the status quo is increasing and expanding (Jibeen & Khan, 2015). As a result, tertiary education graduates are set to be competitively screened with respect to those standards and expectations set either by professionals, institutions, or any organization needing their skills and services or by government institutions (Commission on Higher Education, 2017; República Democrática de Timor - Leste, 2017; Global Partnership for Education, 2020).

Competencies and employability at the university graduate level (or its counterparts), then, are important indicators of the quality of a degree program they were associated with (Cranmer, S., 2006; Klein-Collins, 2012; McClarty & Gaertner, 2015). Given the context, it is therefore interesting to determine whether competencies developed by these individuals during their university degree training and education are relevant and matched for their chosen profession, as well as to the demands of their would-be employers.

Tracing from the year 2002 when Timor-Leste finally had secured its state autonomy, there were visible democratic harmonizing priorities on enacting socio-economic policies rooted in addressing facets of poverty: basic social services, social security, and nation-building, and aiming to foster the country's oil, tourism, and agriculture, among others (World Food Programme, n.d.). The ongoing peace process and state-building are essential to establish a base from which Timor-Leste can address its people's educational, socio-economic, and health necessities. One of the thrusts of East Timor as a newly-emerged democratic nation is to improve its human resources by improving the educational sector, agriculture being one of the important degree programs (Inder, Brown, & Datt, 2014).

Agriculture is regarded as a flagship sector of the country, as it is responsible for 97.7% of exports aside from oil, as well as providing a source of income to eighty-four percent (84%) of the Timor-Leste Labor Force (Timor-Leste Ministry of Finance, 2008, as cited in Inder, Brown, & Datt, 2014). Moreover, as highlighted in the Timor-Leste's 20-year Strategic Development Plan (which covers the years 2011-2030), agriculture plays a crucial role in augmenting the country's prevailing challenges related to poverty mitigation, fostering wellness in rural communities, as well as ensuring food security in every household in Timor-Leste—in form of rural poor responsive and income-generating food production activities (Inder, Brown, & Datt, 2014).

Agriculture is also seen as a vital sector in the Southeast Asian Region (Anik, Rahman, Sarker, 2017; Briones, 2017; Kim, Park, Chun, Li, 2018, as cited by Liu, et.al, 2020). However, the sector is beset with poor productivity and quality because the interest of people to work in agriculture remained underproductive after independence, based on a comprehensive study on trends, prospects and policy direction in the higher education in agriculture. Among countries in Southeast Asia where Timor-Leste is associated, there has been a mixture of trend related to the demographics of enrollees in the field of agriculture.

In the Philippines, according to the Philippine Institute of Development Studies (2017), on average, enrollment in agriculture courses dives by 1.5% annually. In Vietnam, there has been an increasing trend on their graduates from 2006-2008, expecting an expanding professional human resource in their countries agricultural sector (Sheridan, 2010). However, in the recent times, Vietnam's agricultural sector struggles in supplementing enough actual job opportunities for its graduates and new professionals. As agriculture poses elevated economic risks for Vietnam's people—provided the fact that agricultural goods yield cheaper net incomes, specifically on raw materials, interest to participate in agricultural activities has become blurred among prospect workforce, especially to the

youth (Vietnam Union of Science and Technology Associations, 2011). The trend seems to be consistent with the Timor-Leste's context.

One year after the country's independence (2003), there were seventeen (17) accredited higher education institutions (HEIs) by the Directorate of Higher Education, catering to thirteen thousand students pursuing technical, academic, and expert-level curriculum and degree tracks. Within the academic year 2007-2008, HEIs were reduced to fourteen, and these institutions were able to accommodate seventeen thousand students. In 2019, the university serves as second homes to a total of 17,000 students enrolled in Bachelors degree programs. From 2000 to 2018, on the other hand, there were 1,433 Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (BSA) majors in Agronomy program. This degree program has proven its vitality to the country's pursuits for national development, since around 80% of the total population work in the agriculture sector, a priority sector of the government. However, there is an observable decrease in enrolment in the BSA program from 2000 to 2018 (Rejistu Sistema Akademika UNTL Junho, 2018), and this poses risks to more than 80 per cent of the East Timor population, with one million people, who relies on agricultural products and services for food and livelihood (ACIAR, 2015).

Teichler's (2009) perceived contemporary trends in work and employment includes extended reduction of employment in agriculture. There could be various reasons for this. One of the reasons why few students are interested in studying agriculture could be personal choice, especially during his/her secondary education (Onu & Ikehi, 2013). A degree needs to appear interesting to the students and should present good employment prospects—giving impressions to prospect agriculture professionals that income obtained from this line of work entails sense of security for work, better social status, and personal relief (IAAS, 2018).

The impressions on the reputation of the educational institution, on the other hand, can influence a person in the deciding to pursue a higher education track (Onu & Ikehi, 2013). Above all, it is the economic value of higher education that matters to some. Authors such as Brennan, Kogan, and Teichler (1996) and Johnston (2003), as cited in Tomlinson (2012), reiterated that higher education possess associations with the labor market. Higher education provides opportunities and for the labor market for consistent availability of eligible competent professional, skills-based, and managerial workforce.

Graduates of the program Bachelor of Science in Agriculture (BSA) with major in Agronomy are expected to be key sources of knowledge and skills that would help farmers improve their agricultural practices, especially on staple crops. Their ability as Agriculturist-Extension workers in providing quality technical assistance to farmers would be an appropriate key to improve farmers' production performance.

According to Larke *et al.* (1985), among the important competencies among agronomy graduates from the University of Missouri (1971-81) and their respective employers are to 1) determine major row agronomic crops; 2) recognize advantages and disadvantages of tillage practices; 3) interpret soil test results; and 4) identify probably causes of differences within a batch of a particular crop yield. However, the agriculture sector remains problematic as farmers still practice traditional farming methods and worse, there

were lesser students who are interested in BSA Agronomy program. Moreover, there have been no systematic studies on where BSA graduates have become employed; and whether the competencies they possess are desired by the students and current employers, especially in the context of Timor-Leste.

Hence, this article attempts to assess current BSA major in agronomy program of Universidade Nacional de Timor Leste. Accordingly, this could help assess the extension worker's competency and employability of graduates to make the program more attractive to prospective students.

METHODOLOGY

Research Design

The study is a descriptive research. It is referred to as the kind of research question, design, and data analysis applied to the subject matter (Glass & Hopkins, 1984). The major purpose of descriptive research is the description of the state of affairs as it exists at present. This research is concerned with the characteristics of a particular individual or group (Kothari, 2004).

Locale of the Study

Majority of the data collection and observations done for the study was conducted at the Faculty Agriculture UNTL, Ministry of Agriculture. UNTL is a public university located in East Timor. Supporting data and complementary interviews were conducted in local NGO, international NGO, and some municipalities in Timor Leste such as Lospalos district, Liquiçá district, Aileu district, Manatutu district in Natarbora (by telephone) and Bobonaro district (by telephone).

The foundation of UNTL marked a historical event in Timor Leste, as it was founded in 2000, after the nation's independence. There are a total of six campuses, nine colleges, and seven research centers that contributed to the university's reputation as the largest in terms of student and faculty population and financial assets. The headquarters of the university is located in Dili, where the study was primarily conducted.

Figure 1: Photo of UNTL Headquarters, Dili Campus

The municipality of Dili, the central capital of Timor Leste, is located along the northern coastline. Dili is managed by an elected mayor. Among the Administrative Posts or subdistricts of Dili are Nain Feto, Vera Cruz, Dom Aleixo, and Cristo Rei. These posts branch out into *sucos* which are led by the elected *chefe de sucos*. Most (16 out of 26) of these *sucos* are urbanized, while the rest remains as rural areas.

Figure 2: Map of Timor Leste

Research Respondents and Participants

The respondents of this study are the graduates of BSA UNTL and their respective employer. Employers include government, management faculty agriculture UNTL, among others.

The researcher also conducted key informant interviews with the Dean of UNTL Faculty of Agriculture, Director of UNTL Department of Agronomy, Vice Director of UNTL Department of Agronomy, and UNTL Department of Agronomy lecturers. Personal communications were also conducted with the head of the administrative staff of the UNTL Department of Agronomy. A letter was sent to them before the conduct of the research.

Sampling Design and Selection Criteria

The list of agriculture education graduates from 2007-2019 were obtained from the Faculty Agriculture UNTL and served as the sampling frame for the study. The total number of graduate respondents from 2007-2019 was 112.

Meanwhile, the interviewees from UNTL were selected based on their involvement in the BSA program and their position in UNTL. All interviewees have been with UNTL long enough to know the important details about the BSA program.

The employers interviewed were selected based on the number of UNTL BSA Agronomy graduates that are working there for a minimum of six months. With the help of existing community groups online, recommendations from UNTL personnel, and even from the

survey respondents themselves, the directories of employers who have at least three graduates working for them were interviewed about the employee competency rating.

Data Collection

Both primary and secondary data were used in this study. Primary data were collected through survey questionnaires and interviews among members of the groups. The interviews were structured in English and translated into Tetun. Secondary data were gathered from reports of the Faculty of Agriculture UNTL, Department of Agriculture, Department of Statistics, and other related studies.

Initial interviews were done consequently during site visits. The researcher interviewed the director of the department to provide additional information on the current curriculum, extension programs and initiatives, and academic support services they provide to the students. Non-formal interview or small talks and personal conversation were also conducted via telephone and e-mail with the administrative officer, library personnel, and laboratory staff. A follow-up interview was then conducted, with a structured set of questions for complementary information to support the discussion of data collected in the study.

Data Analysis

Data from the survey were processed and analyzed using descriptive statistics such as frequency counts and percentage computations. This determined the general overview on the implications of the respondents' ratings.

On the other hand, the interviews were transcribed and translated into English, and analyzed qualitatively. Interview excerpts that could be used to substantiate the research findings were highlighted and added to the discussions.

To compare the data, the overall mode of the results for each competency category was analyzed. The data compared were 1) the perception of the graduates on the level of emphasis given to the different competencies and the actual level of knowledge that they developed under the program, 2) the employers' rating on the importance of the different competencies and the actual performance of the BSA Agronomy graduate employees, and 3) the graduates' rating on the perceived level of competency skills and the employers' rating on the actual skills that the graduates' perform during their extension work.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Using the research instruments, a total of 112 graduates of the BSA UNTL were surveyed to determine their competencies. Additionally, seven employers and five agricultural lecturers were interviewed with complementary questions to support the following data gathered from the respondents and to assess the core responsibilities of the employers, as well as the teaching methods and approaches related to the development of the graduates' competencies under the BSA program.

Profile of Research Respondents and Participants

Among the BSA graduates, 70 are female and 42 are male. Their ages vary from 28 to 55 years old, but the majority (78.57%) of them are of ages 30 to 39. With regard to their marital status, 96 of them declared that they are married.

Table 1: Personal Information of the BSA Agronomy UNTL graduates

Variables	Frequency(N=112)	Percentage
Sex		
Male	42	37.5
Female	70	62.5
Age		
>30	10	8.93
30-39	88	78.57
40-49	12	10.71
≥50	3	2.68
Civil Status		
Single	16	14.29
Married	96	85.71

The respondents graduated from 2007 to 2019, distributed as shown in the figure below. Almost 43% of the respondents graduated recently, from the year 2015 to 2019.

Figure 3: BSA UNTL's year of graduation distribution

Majority (65%) of the respondents are extension workers, 12% pursued Technical vocation, 9% are in Technical Agriculture work, while the remaining are employed as lecturer, staff, and administrative personnel. The respondents have diverse workplace such as different NGOs, private sector, MoE, MAP, and others. Of the 112 respondents, 48 of them are working or have worked for NGOs.

Table 2: Respondents' occupational information

variables	frequency (N = 112)	percentage (%)
Occupation		
Extension Worker	65	58.04
Technical Agriculture	9	8.04
Technical Vocation	12	10.71
Others (Lecturer, Staff, Former NGO workers)	26	23.21
Workplace		
NGO	48	42.86
Private Sector	17	15.18
MoE	12	10.71
MAP	26	23.21
Others	9	8.04

Meanwhile, some of the employers of the respondents were also profiled. All of them are directors of the workplace and the upper management officials.

The Current BSA Major in Agronomy Program of Universidade

Nacional de Timor Leste

The UNTL describes the BSA Agronomy program as a “course with a main purpose of training qualified professionals to intervene in the agribusiness sector, with dynamism and entrepreneurship.” Additionally, the institution noted that:

The program is with a curricular matrix adjusted to the needs of the market, the student interacts in several areas, relying on disciplines and techniques in the study areas related to soils, irrigation, pests, etc., acting simultaneously with disciplines focused on administration and management, forming a professional prepared for the challenges of the sector.

Dr. Marcal Gusmao, director of the Department of Agronomy, further explained that the program is centered in education where students get science-based information to suffice and secure food production in Timor Leste. The agronomy department pursues the following mission:

- a. Prepare students for entry into professional life with high capacity in the science and technology of agriculture in agronomy,
- b. Develop and progress applied science to education, research and community service,
- c. Develop science and technology in the field of agriculture for national development,
- d. To carry out the learning of education, research and development of the science and technology of agriculture to solve the current problems in this area and monitor the state of the environment and its relationship with agriculture in a sustainable way and ecology,
- e. Guarantee and support science and technology in the context of food security,
- f. Promote science and technology in the context of self-sufficiency in national agro-industry and agro-commerce, and;

g. To form the human person with respect for God, for the country, for the family, for the neighbor and for the Environment.

The curriculum generally takes four years or eight semesters before a student completes all the necessary courses and requirements of the program (Table 3). With the department of agronomy's vision to excel and lead in science and technology in agronomy, the institution strives to provide necessary support for the faculties and the students.

The institution also envisions them to become experts in the field of food production in a national level. Although most of the graduates are offered work and livelihood in the MAP, the department tries to affect student behavior towards researching and looking for solutions for the problems in the agricultural sector, both on the local and national scale. Additionally, they want the graduates to be globally competitive as they pursue additional academic years in other countries or region and expand their knowledge and experience further.

The program trains and educates the students using various approaches to tackle both theoretical concepts and practical applications of agronomy. As shown in Table 3, the students are required to take a total of 240 credit points, with 60 units each year. On their first year, the subjects they need to take are language courses such as Portuguese, English, and Tetum in levels I and II. Additionally, they need to take introductory courses like Basic Mathematics, Introduction to Agricultural Production System, and Introduction to Agribusiness, as well as General Biology, Chemistry and Civic, Ethic, and Moral Education.

On their second year, they are required to take more hard science courses such as Statistics, Biochemistry, Crop Production, Plant Protection, Agro-Climatology, Basics of Soil Science, Ecology, Microbiology, Agronomy Science, Agricultural Mechanization, Preservation of Genetic Resources, and Agricultural Extension. Physics used to be part of the old BSA Agronomy curriculum, but it is no longer required at present.

Their junior years will be comprised of Soil Fertilization Science, Irrigation and Drainage, Plant Breeding, Horticulture Science, Plant Physiology, Agricultural Experimental Design, Soil and Water Conservation, Industrial Plants Science, Weed Science, Tissue Culture, Field Practice and Services, and Agro-Fruit and Vegetables.

During their senior years, they are tasked to produce quality research materials using the research tools and strategies that were taught to them from their first semester until their last year in the academe. Their required courses are Entrepreneurship, Post-Harvest Technology, Agricultural Research Method, Seed Technology, Medicinal Plants, Backyard Garden and Cultivation, Social Service and Practices, Seminar and Thesis. Their last semester is comprised only of three courses, but these courses hold important learning experiences to prepare them into the agricultural world after they graduate. The Social Service and Practices will be credited with 10 points, the Seminar with 5 points, and the Thesis with 15 points. As such, these subjects should not be taken very lightly. Furthermore, the management allows the students, especially the seniors, to conduct

fieldworks in partner communities and organizations to earn experiences that they will not experience in class. The subject KKN or the Social Service and Practice is the main internship activity that the students need to undergo. With a duration of about a month or two, the students are tasked to work with a community and gather knowledge from their experiences there. The main purpose of this immersion is to let the students observe, familiarize, and apply some of the farmer’s practices and incorporate their theoretical groundings into the daily situations of the farmers and the community they are working with.

Table 3: New structure of the BSA agronomy curriculum offered in UNTL

Year & Semester	Code of Subject Matter	Name of Subject Matter	Credit Point	Year & Semester	Code of Subject Matter	Name of Subject Matter	Credit Point
Sem 1	UNA01	Portuguese Language I	4	Sem 5	AG030	Soil Fertilization Science	6
	UNA01	English Language I	4		AG031	Irrigation and Drainage	4
	UNA101	Tetum Language I	4		AG032	Plant Breeding	4
	FA01	General Biology	6		AG033	Horticulture Science	4
	FA02	Introduction to Agricultural Production System	6		AG034	Plant Physiology	6
Y1	UNA07	Mathematic Basic	6	Y3	AGO35	Agricultural Experimental Design	6
	UNA04	Portuguese Language II	5		AG068	Soil and Water Conservation	6
Sem 2	UNA02	English Language II	5	Sem 6	AG054	Industrial Plants Science	6
	UN105	Tetum Language II	5		AG043	Weed Science	6
	UNA07	Civic, Ethic and Moral Education	3		AG044	Tissue Culture	4
	AG 062	Chemistry	6		FA057	Field Practice and Services	4
	AG 036	Introduction to Agribusiness	6		FA058	Agro-Fruit and Vegetables	4
Sem 3	AG 040	Statistics	4	Sem 7	AG050	Entrepreneurship	4
	AG 041	Biochemistry	4		AG051	Post Harvest Technology	6
	AG 042	Crop Production	6		AG052	Agricultural Research Method	6
	AG 043	Plant Protection	6		AG053	Seed Technology	6
	AG 064	Agro-Climatology	4		AG054	Medicinal Plants	4
Y2	AG 045	Basic of soil Science	6	Y4	AG055	Backyard Garden and Cultivation	4
	AG 056	Ecology and Environment	4		UNA10	Social Service and Practices	10
	AG 065	Microbiology	6		Sem 8	AG029	Seminar
Sem 4	AG 060	Agronomy Science	6	AG030	Thesis	15	
	AG 067	Agricultural Mechanization	5				
	AG 045	Preservation of Genetic Resources	5				
	AG 046	Agricultural Extension	4	TOTAL Credit Point		240	

Delfin da costa, the Deputy Director of the Department of Agronomy, said that UNTL focused on the development of teaching and learning environment supports such as the e-library that the students can access for resources and academic references. In addition to this, the department also upgraded the laboratory facilities for the students to utilize. However, since UNTL as a public institution strictly complies on budget spending guidelines, the needed advancements and solutions for most of the challenges they face often takes a while.

Despite this, the UNTL further supports innovation ideas that can improve the quality of teaching and learning through partnerships with research centers or think tanks experts, other institutions and learning departments, and national agencies in and out of the country, to provide multi-faceted learning experience to the students. Gusmao hopes for their graduates to become leaders of the agricultural sector that provides guidance and problem-solving initiatives for the issues and challenges in the said industry. The institution invested on implementing tools and adopting technologies for more advanced digital analysis the students can utilize.

The department assigned people in charge of monitoring the quality of teaching in the institution. UNTL associates are highly encouraged to improve instruction delivery by following international policies, trends, and benchmarks. Thus, lecturers are also encouraged to actively participate in research and publication studies to enhance their knowledge and perspectives on different fields and area of expertise. Gomez and Panaligan (2013) view research as one of the indicators when assessing the competencies of education professionals. They noted that academic reputation of an educator is dependent on his or her ability to “investigate scientifically, to come up with new ideas, knowledge, and new discoveries” that can contribute to the improvement of the institution’s practices and strategies. Roane, et al., (2009) added that in ensuring research competency, production of research outputs and projects should be mandated in an institution.

Da Acosta identified the field work in crop science as the BSA program’s strength, while digital-related approaches are tagged as its weakness. Although the lecturers revise the curriculum every five years, it takes them at least six months to do such revisions. According to Selvi’s research on teachers’ competency in 2010, curriculum competencies related to understanding the program and the curriculum requiring theoretical and practical skills are important especially since its main goal is to develop, organize, and strategize content and learning outcomes of the course or field. Without this competency, it will be a challenge for the institution to produce effective academic and educational service.

Teaching Methods for the Development of Extension Worker’s Competencies in the BSA Program

The teaching methods employed in the Department of Agronomy in UNTL as observed in this study are comprised of classroom-based activities and field work or laboratory exercises. Upon the start of the semester, the goal of the instruction is to familiarize the

students with the basic concepts and principles that they can learn inside the classroom. Consequently, the lecturers and professors will incorporate hands on activities that they can perform either on the field or in their laboratories.

Since the courses offered in the department vary from Chemical, Biology, Biochemical, Microbiology, Soil fertility, etc., some of these activities could not be learned by just theoretical and conceptual methods of teaching. The students experienced planting crops in the available land at Campus II in Hera as part of their Horticulture exercises. For the field work, the graduate students visited the School Agriculture Fuloro in Lospalos District, a famous Catholic mission school. They also visited Loes, a sub-district of Liquisa district, where the Research Agriculture Center of the Ministry of Agriculture is located. Lastly, they visited Horticulture Center of USAID in Aileu District.

According to the students, there were many activities during the field trip, and they were given opportunities to ask questions and get information on agricultural crops, thereby improving their knowledge. However, in the table of effectiveness as noted by five UNTL BSA Agronomy lecturers, this method of teaching is only somewhat effective. Although it is true that the students get to compare what they had learned in class to the reality in the field, sometimes the travel can be very long. This makes the students tired, thereby affecting the students' capacity and motivation to learn.

Aside from this, the students are also introduced to a community where they can observe, ask questions, and take note of how the professional farmers act on the field. However, some of the UNTL graduates noted that they lack the tools and equipment for farming activities when they practice crop planting, as well as the proper crop planting demonstration. Some also noted how they lack exposure to production of media materials such as leaflets, brochures, news articles, and such. Additionally, they also noticed that some of the information taught in the class are outdated.

Majority of the lecturers agreed that they highly used examinations, survey, lecture, overhead projector, team teaching, using real objectives, and field works. Although demonstrations were noted as slightly used by the lecturers, all of them agreed that this method is highly effective along with lecture discussions, examinations, overhead projector, using real objectives, and field work. Adekoya and Olatoye (2011) noted in their study that demonstration strategy as a teaching method resulted with positive significant change in student's academic achievements. They noted that students get more motivation through this teaching method because they experience to interact with the professionals in a free manner. Additionally, demonstration sessions were noted as an effective way to promote and develop thinking skills and student creativity, as well as in improving their attitude towards the subject being taught (Basheer, 2017).

On the other hand, the lecturers reported that they never use television as a method of teaching but rated it very effective. Mohammed and Haroun (2017) explored the role of instructional television as an approach for effective teaching method to solve poor academic performance of Nigerian schools. The study concluded that instructional television has a significant positive effect on academic performance since their attitudes and interest towards the subject increases when the device is used as a medium for

teaching. However, Patidar (2020) noted that the challenge in this mode of instruction is how serious and determined the instructors or lecturers are in using the television. He added that this is an essential tool as a helping hand in education, as such, should only be used as a complementary to other teaching methods.

Available Academic Support Services for Faculty and Students

Capacity Building Programs. The university sends out representatives to international activities as another means of capacity building. As such, tangible incentives are also given for constituents who showed teaching improvements through an evaluation process. An internal quality assurance team monitors and spearheads activities that involve fostering teaching and instruction delivery improvements.

Consequently, the department of agronomy used to conduct exchange programs for students yearly. According to Gusmao, they used to send off students to Israel every year for an opportunity to learn more about the field of agronomy in a different weather and climate setting. This exchange program is funded by the Israel government, so it is free. A lot of exchanged students learned a lot of agricultural and horticultural techniques that they show off when they get back at Timor Leste.

To avail of the exchange program, the most important requirement is a basic understanding and conversing using the English language. Most of the students who gets accepted in the program are students with senior standing. This program generally lasts for six months, but there are certain cases that it extends up to nine months.

Internships and Scholarships. UNTL supports additional learning opportunities like this to immerse students in a holistic view of situations in the agricultural sector even in other countries like Israel. They can grow and look for different perspectives as they interact with the locals in the destination country. However, they no longer offer exchange programs at the present.

The faculty tries to let the students work with partner companies for first-hand demonstrations of food production and technology. Da Acosta mentioned that the institution believes this integration is a preparation for their future encounters.

Aside from this, there are also opportunities for student assistance in terms of scholarships. Gusmao also mentioned that lecturers can sign up for these scholarships if they want to pursue their education further. Some of the known scholarships are provide by the government and universities from Portugal and Brazil. Since Timor Leste adopted the Portuguese language as one of their official languages, they are being screened for opportunities in studying in these countries. Additionally, SEARCA provides scholarships for students. An Indonesian university also tapped UNTL a couple of times as they offered funding lecturers who wants to expand their knowledge in the field of agriculture in Indonesia. Gusmao noted that in the past, they used to have a few PhD lecturers. As time passed by, lecturers with doctorate degrees are increasing in the faculty.

This scholarship for the lecturers is sometimes endorsed by the department. The institution often selects notable lecturers and faculty of the year and invites them for such opportunity to enhance their teaching capabilities more. However, a major requirement for this is the ability to speak in Portuguese language or whatever the destination country's language is.

For PhD students, the scholarship takes about four or five years. The government of Timor Leste usually finances these scholarships as long as they are able to perform well in their academics. However, Gusmao narrated that salary deduction is one of the downsides of this academic pursuit as the lecturer's salary for teaching are paused when they are studying.

Implications and Recommended Strategies for

BSA Agronomy Program Development

Based on Empirical Analysis

Improvement of educational facilities and infrastructure for student utilization. After site visits and conduct of the research in the UNTL, the researcher noted points that may be improved in the university. For instance, the classrooms and other facilities in the institution seemed small for a class of 50 students. Additionally, some students during the interview noted that they find it hard to focus on their classes due to the constricting and limited space they can utilize as their learning environment. As such, it is recommended to adjust the classroom population or to restructure the classrooms to be able to fit and accommodate students with comfort and adequate space for learning.

Subsequently, it was also noted that the university library is not spacious enough to accommodate a lot of students simultaneously. Libraries and other facilities like these are important in boosting the overall attitude of students when it comes to learning and researching. These types of environments should be conducive for education purposes, so that the students, educators, and the management itself can fully maximize the utilization of such areas.

Additional support services and facility enhancement for students and faculty members. The libraries could use computer units to help both students and faculties in familiarizing with technology. The institution could provide basic internet access inside the university. The internet and other teaching and learning tools online can be a massive help to the constituents of UNTL.

Consequently, providing the students with experiences from fieldworks, exchange programs, and internship-like activities can also boost their attitude in learning. These activities, if possible, should be brought back by the department. However, some re-assessments should be done to make the selection process more organized and centralized.

On the other hand, the department can utilize the land in the second campus, Hera, for field activities such as planting crops, vegetables, horticulture activities, and even research. Furthermore, the department should create a center of training for extension

workers as an important element in an agronomy student's learning process, as well as forging relationships with the people and communities they have worked together. This can serve as an avenue to gather information and evaluate with stakeholders to establish organizational and strategical plans.

Based on Interviews with Graduates, Faculties, and Administrative Personnel

During the interview with the graduates and the other key informant for the study, a few gaps emerged on their experience-based and varied view on the factors that affect the quality of education the students receive in the UNTL.

Educational resources being utilized in class. The graduates also mentioned that the materials being used in their lectures, as well as the available resources in the library, are mostly outdated. Paolini (2015) noted that effective instruction delivery always starts with teachers prioritizing the materials and resources needed to meet the course learning's objectives. In this regard, the educational resources used in class will primarily depend on the objectives of the course. To ensure maximum effectivity, both the resources and the learning objectives for each course should be reviewed.

Additionally, Weimer (2006) noted that the teaching content is as important as the teaching methods as they are "inextricably linked and co-dependent". Emphasizing the quality of the teaching content being used in instructional delivery is a key player for high student academic performance, as well as their excellence after outside the university after they graduate.

It is also a department or institutional initiative to invest on the tools and equipment needed in class. Since demonstration is an effective learning method, a successful application of such will require proper and functional equipment. As such, this also ensure that they do not only experience the learning first-hand, but also performs it safely.

Adopting technological and digital approaches to improve institutional competency. During the KII, Da Acosta mentioned digital-related activities and initiatives as the institution's weakness. Using modern means of instructional delivery such as software, multi-media platform, the internet, and other digital approaches increases the possibility of enriching the learning process (Maksimovic & Dimic, 2016).

In this case, such application of ICTs, digital, and technological approaches is a way to keep in trend of institutional competency. The establishment of an e-library can also become an integral advantage for their students. As such, having digital-related technologies entail the basic know-hows on operating devices and technologies involved in it. The institution should provide complementary programs to guide the students and the faculties on how to use digital tools in teaching and learning. Maksimovic and Dimic (2016) suggested that enhancing educator's strengths in the use of technology and digital initiatives are necessary to improve their competencies as professionals. The study recommends integration of more practices, conducting workshops and training, and other complementary activities that can aid the UNTL lecturers in handling digital and

technological tools to further improve their educational and professional competencies, as well as the institution's competitiveness in the academic field.

Policies that benefit and prioritize BSA Agronomy student graduates. The department should also forge a memorandum of agreement for 1) the ministry to prioritize UNTL graduates in hiring extension workers, and 2) provide opportunities for the existing extension workers' technical vocational and senior high school to continue their study in UNTL with a degree or formal schooling. BSA Agronomy students should at least be prioritized when considering an extension work position because of the training and educational groundings they have received in the university, as well as the technical opportunities they have been exposed to on their senior years.

Partnership with communities and field workers. According to the interview with the graduates, they do not have activities to teach the farmers or people in the community on how to resolve agricultural problems such as using fertilizers and applications of farming practices, among others. Curwood, et al., (2011) recommended in their research to always keep in mind that engaging the communities in university activities forms a collaborative relationship. In that regard, it is necessary that they share common values and commitment to the learning activity, as well as the community service that they intend to act with their partner stakeholders.

The study recommends that rather than just building short-term community-related partnerships, they forge their relationships and reciprocate the time and effort of the farmers in aiding the university in their learning endeavors. These farmers and community groups should also be included in the formulation of learning activities and outputs. The institution can turnover materials or outputs that can help farmers in their agricultural activities to reciprocate their dedication in helping with the field demonstrations.

Based on Analysis of Perceived and Actual Competency Ratings

Considering the data presented in the previous sections, the BSA Agronomy's curriculum needs another approach in their teaching strategy. Most of the competency related areas were tackled with much emphasis, but still ended up with lower level of skills as rated by the graduates themselves.

Method of instruction and teaching strategies. Paolini (2015) suggests that conducting a "post mortem" on the lecturer's lesson is important for them to identify and reflect on the extent of participation, understanding, motivation, and attitude the students have towards his method of teaching. As such, an assessment or evaluation and re-alignment of strategies is important to create a cycle of continuous improvement of the instruction and the curriculum itself. Venturing in a learner-centered perspective may also boost competencies of the students. In this case, it is more efficient and tactical for the institution to re-strategize their curriculum and develop it to fit the generation of their learners while ensuring the quality of education that they are catering as a globally competitive academic institution. Additionally, Daluba (2013) noted that conventional lecture methods may be effective to students, but not on the long run especially when it

is the only method of teaching used in the classroom setup. Li (2016) mentioned that conventional teaching classroom should also be learner-centered and should facilitate the use of multi-mediated learning strategies.

BSA Agronomy lecturers should consider incorporating such recommendations since a few of the graduates noted that they have low problem-solving skills and other analytical related competencies. Although the majority of lecturers interviewed noted that they use problem solving approaches frequently, it is essential to note that they only view this approach as somewhat effective. Critical and analytical thinking skills are essential to employers in almost all fields of work. As such, conventional lecturers should not be the sole method of teaching in the program since its biggest disadvantage is its ineffectiveness in higher order thinking skills as it also hinders student creativity and lessens their motivation because of the long hours of being passive listeners (Marmah, 2014).

Burton (2003) noted the use of differentiation as an aspect of a teacher's professional competence that ensures each student's achievement of the intended learning outcome that he or she set for the course. Coffey (2007) added that effective instructors utilize varieties of learning modes to try to fit into every student's learning style and capacity as schools should be the primary responsible for adapting to their developmental needs.

Educational resources utilized in class. One factor that might contribute to the low level of skills of the graduates is the mentioned gap by some of the interviewees in terms of the materials and content of lectures that they use in class. The graduates mentioned that even the available resources in the library are mostly outdated. Paolini (2015) noted that effective instruction delivery always starts with teachers prioritizing the materials and resources needed to meet the course learning's objectives. In this regard, the educational resources used in class will primarily depend on the objectives of the course. To ensure maximum effectivity, both the resources and the learning objectives for each course should be reviewed.

Additionally, Weimer (2006) noted that the teaching content is as important as the teaching methods as they are "inextricably linked and co-dependent". Emphasizing the quality of the teaching content being used in instructional delivery is a key player for high student academic performance, as well as their excellence after outside the university after they graduate.

It is also a department or institutional initiative to invest on the tools and equipment needed in class. Since demonstration is an effective learning method, a successful application of such will require proper and functional equipment. As such, this also ensures that they do not only experience the learning first-hand, but also performs it safely.

Assessment and re-structuring the program or curriculum. The most important step to prioritize is to take into consideration the results of the comparison of the perceived and actual level of competence of the graduates as perceived by both themselves and their employers. The individual mode interpretations also reflected that some that

although is just averagely emphasized, is still rated with high skills. This means that the department can set back on the very emphasized topics and see why it only contributes to lower level of knowledge than those that are only averagely emphasized. They can explore on the current methods of instruction that they use in class because some of it may no longer be effective for the present student learning needs. Giving opportunity for scholarly research activities to students can challenge their perspective and require them to think beyond what is being taught in the classroom. This will inspire them to further contribute to available sources of information and knowledge as it simultaneously forces them to think critically and to find in-depth reflections of their own level of knowledge regarding their pursued area of expertise.

Lynch (2008) commented that connecting the curricula to the student's lives and experiences will open opportunities for innovation of knowledge and will enable them to apply it in solving relevant issues of the society. Techniques such as targeting maximum learning (asking higher-order critical thinking questions, problem-based learning, case studies, computer-based learning), critical reflection (logs, journals, collaborative learning), and inquiry (small group learning) can also be explored or used more frequently as a substitute for the conventional ways of teaching.

CONCLUSIONS AND RECOMMENDATIONS

Conclusions

The gap between all the comparisons shows the need to restructure the curriculum of the BSA Agronomy program. The current methods and approaches that they employ in teaching their students may not fully provide high satisfaction to the employers in the long run.

Although there is no deeper correlational assessment on these variables and how it directly affects the acquired skills and knowledge, some of the respondents interviewed noted that their skills were not enhanced enough due to limited strategies employed in their classes. As such, more field demonstrations, hands on exercises, and immersion activities with local farmers were suggested in their survey responses.

Additionally, some of the UNTL personnel noted that they need to improve their educational resources, ICT services, and other supporting initiatives. They have observed that some of their teaching practices and materials are already outdated. Likewise, their facilities need to be improved.

Recommendations

Using the identified issues and hindrances in the curriculum, teaching strategies, and available academic resources and services, the following recommendations were formulated:

For UNTL

Application of ICTs and strengthening of digital and technological approaches.

The institution should be able to adapt to the digital competency demands that most of the industries and sectors across the globe face at the present. Provision of internet in the campus for the use of all the students and faculties should be considered to bridge the digital divide that is existing among the students of UNTL.

Forging partnerships for UNTL BSA Agronomy graduate prioritization in extension program related works.

The university takes its pride in producing exemplary students. As such, forming partnerships and reaching out to other universities and institutions for opportunities before and after their graduation is always a good idea to ensure that the students have enough motivation and challenge as they take on their academic years.

Providing additional academic aids for student utilization.

In 2019, a global pandemic brought about by a new strain of corona virus called COVID-19 affected the entire population, industries, and sectors in almost all the countries across the globe. Due to severe effects of the virus that targets the respiratory and immune system of people regardless of age, lockdowns and community quarantine protocols were implemented. This affected the educational sector, as face to face classes were suspended and alternatively done online. Additional aids such as computers and other digital devices should be provided in order to teach both the students and the faculty members on how to handle such technologies. Digital literacy is among the most sought for competency especially now that we are facing a pandemic crisis that forces us to connect through other people by online means.

Planning investments and facility enhancement proposals for funding.

It was noted that even though the facilities like laboratories, classrooms, and the library are fully functional, they no longer suffice the needs of the students for a conducive and much more optimal learning environment. The spaces for learning should be able to cater more students simultaneously without compromising the comfort of each student. As such, infrastructure redevelopment and investment should be taken into account as soon as possible.

For Department of Agronomy

Competency enhancement programs for faculties and students.

The department should plan and allocate resources into programs and activities that enables capacity building for both their members and students. As such, they can bring back opportunities such as participating in international academic activities and other programs that are emerging during these times.

Regular monitoring and evaluation of curriculum and assessment of appropriateness and effectiveness of methods of instruction.

This should be done not just to monitor the staff and faculty, but to give them recognition for their efforts and initiatives in teaching. One of the benefits of doing such assessments is that they can also reflect on the strategies that they are using to know which of them are still effective and

which are no longer appropriate to the current learner needs of this generation, given all the circumstances that they are facing.

For Faculty Members of Agriculture

Restructuring of curriculum to fit learner needs. Curriculum development should not be done after five or more years. Doing further immediate actions to target the issues that surfaced from curriculum evaluation is much more essential. Addressing such gaps and shortcomings of the curriculum should be the priority of the faculty members to ensure the quality of the courses that they are offering.

Additionally, this restructuring entails onboarding the faculty members with the changes that they need to face once they teach the new curriculum to their students. The utmost preparation that the faculty needs to do is to equip each of them in the teaching force to be familiar and knowledgeable in the revisions that will be made or has been made in the curriculum.

Updating classroom sources of information. It is essential to ensure that the content and context that the faculty use in teaching are relevant and updated. Faculties and lecturers should always make sure that their learning materials are up-to-date and appropriate for the current situations.

Exploring effective modes of instruction and strengthening teaching strategies. Some of the teaching strategies employed in the classes are usually no longer effective to the students. However, the faculty and lecturers need to seek feedback from their students on what strategies or methods are most effective for them. In doing so, they can re-strategize on how they should deliver their lectures and lessons in class that most suit their learners.

Leveling off with the expectations of employers in the industry. Since the results of the comparison of the ratings between the employers and the graduates have gaps, the institution and the department should assess what measures should be done to fit in the employers' and the industry's demands in terms of the quality of employees that they usually hire. If the quality of competencies of the graduates as an employee do not meet what they are expected to do, this may effect the next generation of graduates in terms of favorability and employability.

Regularly assessing and monitoring the effectiveness of the teaching methods employed for competency-related topics in class. The varying levels of emphasis and the acquired competence based on the graduates' rating should be considered in restructuring the curriculum and assessing if the program is still effective in terms of producing globally and locally competitive set of students. Since the data showed that high levels of emphasis may sometimes not be enough to ensure a high level of knowledge and skills, the department should explore different approaches in teaching such competencies and triangulating what does not work in the current system and what works that can be applied to other situations and subject matters.

For Further Research

Since the study only provided a descriptive analysis of the UNTL BSA Agronomy graduates' competencies as well as the current teaching strategies and curriculum of the program, a more detailed and explorative approach to the study. The correlation of variables can also be further examined to provide a more concrete indication of how a factor affects another. Since the study only utilized the comparison of the general modes of each competency, some data may not have been probed enough in this study. This will then result to a better, targeted, and context-specific strategies that can help the institution and other institutions with similar situations in their program development and re-evaluation.

Literature Cited

- 1) Adekoya, Y., & Olatoye, R. (2011). Effect of demonstration, peer-tutoring, and lecture teaching strategies on senior secondary school students' achievement in an aspect of agricultural students. *The Pacific Journal of Science and Technology* 12(1), p 329.
- 2) Basheer, A. (2017). The effectiveness of teachers' use of demonstrations for enhancing students' understanding of and attitudes to learning the oxidation-reduction concept. *Eurasia Journal of Mathematics, Science and Technology Education* 13(3), p 555-570.
- 3) Brennan, J., Kogan, M., & Teichler, U. (1996) *Higher Education and Work*, London: Jessica Kingsley
- 4) Coffey, S. (2007). Differentiation in theory and practice. In *Becoming a teacher: Issues in secondary education*, 3rd ed., Edited by: Dillon, J. and Maguire, M., 187–201, Berkshire: Open University Press.
- 5) Cranmer, S. (2006) 'Enhancing graduate employability: Best intentions and mixed outcome', *Studies in Higher Education* 31(2): 169–184 Timor- Leste National Strategic Plan for Education 2011-2015.
- 6) Curwood, S., Munger, F., Mitchell, T., Mackeigen, M., & Farrar, A. (2011). Building effective community-university partnerships: Are universities truly ready? *Michigan Journal of Community Service Learning*, 17(2) p 15-28.
- 7) Gomez, M., & Panaligan, C. (2013). Level of research competencies and satisfaction of the faculty members from the College of Criminology. *Asian Academic Research* 1(14), p 270.
- 8) Glass, G.V. And Hopkins, K.D. (1984). *Statistical methods in education and psychology*, 2nd ed. Englewood Cliffs, NJ: Prentice-Hall.
- 9) Inder, B., Brown, A., & Datt, G. (2014). *Poverty and the Agricultural Household in TimorLeste: Some Patterns and Puzzles*. MONASH Centre for Development Economics and Sustainability Research Paper Series on Timor-Leste. Retrieved from <http://seedsoflifetimor.org/wp-content/uploads/2014/12/Monash-Timor-research-paper-June2014.pdf>
- 10) Johnston, B. (2003). 'The shape of research in the field of higher education and graduate employment: Some issues', *Studies in Higher Education* 28(4): 413–426.
- 11) KOTHARI, C.R. (2004). *Research methodology: Methods and techniques*, 2nd ed. New Delhi: New Age International Publishers.
- 12) Li, Y. (2016). Transforming conventional teaching classroom to learner-centered teaching classroom using multimedia-mediated learning modules. *International Journal of Information and Education Technology* 6(2) p. 105.
- 13) Lynch, D. J. (2008). Confronting challenges: Motivational beliefs and learning strategies in difficult college courses. *College Student Journal*, 42, 416–421.

- 14) Marmah, A. (2014). Students' perception about the lecture as a method of teaching in tertiary institutions; views of student from College of Technology Education, Kumasi (Coltek). *International Journal of Education and Research* 2(6) p. 605.
- 15) Maksimovic, J., & Dimic, N. (2016). Digital technology and teacher's competence for its application in the classroom. *Research in Pedagogy* 6(2) p 59-71.
- 16) Mohammed, M., & Haroun, H. (2017). Instructional television: A multimedia approach for effective teaching and a viable solution to poor students' academic performance in Nigerian schools. *Journal of Research and Method in Education* 7(1) p 22-26.
- 17) Onu, F.M., & Ikehi, M.E. (2013). Factors Influencing Students' Choice to Study Agricultural Science in South-South Nigeria. *Journal of Agriculture and Biodiversity Research*. ISSN 2277- 0836; Volume 2, Issue 4, pp. 80-86.
- 18) Paolini, A. (2015). Enhancing teaching effectiveness and student learning outcomes. *The Journal of Effective Teaching* 15(1) p 20-33.
- 19) Philippine Institute for Development Studies (2017, September 19). Free Tuition to Shore Up Enrollment in Agriculture Courses. Retrieved from <https://pids.gov.ph/pidsin-the-news/2132>.
- 20) Roane, D.M., Idan, E., Haeri, S., & Galynker I. I. (2009) Ensuring Research Competency in Psychiatric Residency Training. *Academic Psychiatry*. Retrieved from <http://ap.psychiatryonline.org>.
- 21) Sheridan, G. (2010). Preparing the Higher Education Sector Development Project— Developing New Model Universities (NMU) in Vietnam. Asian Development Bank Technical Assistance Consultant's Report. Retrieved from <https://www.adb.org/sites/default/files/projectdocument/63092/42079-01-vie-tacr-03>
- 22) Vietnam Union of Science and Technology Associations. (2011). Research Report on rural labour and employment in Viet Nam. International Labour Organization, ISBN: 978-92-2-125716-5. Retrieved from https://www.ilo.org/wcmsp5/groups/public/---asia/---robangkok/---ilo-hanoi/documents/publication/wcms_171760.pdf. Wan Nooraini W, & Mohammed, S. (2010). Lecturer efficacy, professional and general competencies of Malaysian polytechnic technical lecturers. [Paper Proceedings].
- 23) Weimer, M. (2006). Content knowledge a barrier to teacher development. *Effective Strategies for Improving College Teaching and Learning: The Teaching Professor*, Magna Publications.